

Bootstrap confidence interval approach to compare bioavailability of nasal levodopa microspheres vs intranasal levodopa carbidopa formulation in brain

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Abstract : The comparative pharmacokinetic study of levodopa (l-dopa) nasal microspheres (test) and l-dopa carbidopa (c-dopa) nasal formulation (reference) was carried out on 120 healthy experimental rats in 20 groups. The concentration of l-dopa in brain was determined by LC/MS-MS. All pharmacokinetic parameters were calculated using a non-compartmental model. 90% bootstrap confidence interval (CI) of test/reference AUC and C_{max} ratio were calculated to access bioavailability. The ratio and 90% CI for nasal l-dopa/nasal l-dopa+c-dopa formulation was 96.94 (60.05–133.83) for C_{max} and 92.29 (66.54–118.04) for AUC_t . Despite 90% CI limit not within the bioequivalence limit of 80% to 125% both formulation are equivalent at ratio test. The above statement is further proved by student t-test as probability of detecting difference between above formulations, at 95% CI was 0.547 which signifies there is no significant difference between two formulations. Therefore it can be concluded that bioadhesive nasal microspheres containing l-dopa alone can be used in treatment of Parkinson's disease.

Keywords : Parkinson's disease, non-compartment model, serial sacrifice design, pharmacokinetic parameters.

Introduction

Average bioequivalence is commonly tested for pharmacokinetic (PK) parameters (e.g. AUC and C_{max}) obtained from bioequivalence studies of crossover or parallel design. Generally, $\log(AUC)$ and $\log(C_{max})$ values are statistically analyzed using the mixed effect or two-stage linear model. This two stage analysis procedure involves estimation of AUCs and C_{max} in first stage for each analysis subject separately, and the second stage uses the individual parameters estimates for statistical inference. Based on the two-one sided test proposed by Shuirmann (FDA, 2001)¹, two formulations are claimed to be bioequivalent when the 90% confidence intervals (CIs) of mean $\log(AUC)$ differences and $\log(C_{max})$ differences fall within the regulatory acceptance limits [$\log(0.8)$ to $\log(1.25)$]. The mean differences in $\log(AUC)$ or $\log(C_{max})$ between the test and the reference formulation represent the formulation effect, a key parameter in the ABE test².

To obtain statistical inference from the SSD samples, distribution independent simulation is to be applied to generate numerous PK metrics. Bootstrap method use

resampling techniques to simulate independent sample for statistical inference. Instead of generating observations from a known theoretical distribution as before, observations were generated from the distribution of the sample itself – the empirical distribution. Each simulation results in a new sample^{3,4}. Each bootstrap sample is typically similar sample size as the original, by randomly selecting (with replacement) individuals from the original sample. With replacement means that at each step in the selection process, every individual from the original sample is again eligible to get selected, whether or not he has already been selected. Thus, in each bootstrap sample, some of the original individuals may not be represented and others may be represented more than once⁵.

The hypothesis of this study is that a constant plasma level of l-dopa would overcome the motor complications (such as dyskinesia) associated with the use of oral dosage form containing c-dopa in Parkinson's patients. Hence, prepared HPMC-Carbopol 934p microspheres of l-dopa were subjected to animal study to compare bioavailability between nasal levodopa (l-dopa) microspheres and nasal levodopa+carbidopa (c-dopa) preparations.

Experimental

All animal experiments adhered to the Principles for Biomedical Research involving animals developed by the Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences. Male Sprague-Dawley (SD) rats weighing between 180–280 g were involved in the study. Animal study protocol was approved by Ethiconsult services (S-11-233) and carried out in Microtherapeutics India Pvt. Ltd. All surgical procedures were performed under anaesthesia with ether, and an intra-peritoneal injection of 0.2 mL/kg xylazine with 0.2 mL/kg tiletamine-xolazepam was given for deeper anaesthesia and immobilization. 120 rats were divided into two groups – First group for levodopa +carbidopa administration (reference-60) and second group (test-60) for levodopa microsphere administration and sub grouped with 6 rats per time points.

Serial sacrifice design (SSD) approach was used to collect brain sample. Due to difficulty in measuring drug concentration in the brain at 8–12 time points in the same animal, SSD was chosen to characterize PK profile of levodopa. As per design one animal was assigned for only one time point hence at least 6 animals was chosen to establish statistical significant difference between the time points⁶.

The formulation of l-dopa (2.5 mg/kg)/c-dopa (0.63 mg/kg) and l-dopa microspheres alone (2.5 mg/kg) were administered into one nostril using a microsyringe. Brain samples were collected at predose and at 0.08, 0.16, 0.25, 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 8 and 12 h. Total 120 rats were used in this study because each rat was assigned only one time point due to decapitation. The brain was removed quickly and weighed. The brain (1 g) sample being snap-frozen on liquid nitrogen and stored at –70 °C until analyzed.

Study medications :

The test product, l-dopa (Divi's Lab, Hyderabad, Andhra Pradesh, India) microsphere formulation was developed by East Point College of Pharmacy, Bangalore, Karnataka, India and the reference was obtained from product Hetero Drugs Limited, Hyderabad, Andhra Pradesh, India.

Brain preparations :

Preparation of standard calibration curve :

For the preparation of brain standard solutions or

samples, the frozen brains were ground using mortar and pestle. Working stock solutions of l-dopa and d3 levodopa (internal standard, IS) were prepared in water at a concentration of 1 ng/mL. Prior to use, the stock solutions of l-dopa and IS were further diluted with water to obtain working solutions. An appropriate dilution of the working solution with drug-free brain homogenate gave l-dopa concentration between 50 and 1000 pg/mL.

Blank brain extract were prepared from the fresh brain of the rat. Two-hundred microliters of the IS (10 pg/mL aqueous solution) and 100 µL of 4 M perchloric acid was added to 1 mL of brain homogenate, then vortex-mixed for 2 min and centrifuged at 9000 rpm for 20 min. A 300 µL aliquot of the supernatant was added to 200 µL of 2 M potassium citrate buffer (pH 3.8) to precipitate the perchlorate. Each tube was vortexed for 1 min and then centrifuged. 20 µL aliquots of the clear supernatant were injected onto the LC-MS/MS system for analysis.

Pharmacokinetics analysis :

Individual subject mean concentration data was plotted (using sparse sampling technique for serial sacrifice design analysis) against each time points to determine primary pharmacokinetic parameters like C_{max} , AUC_t , AUC_{inf} and secondary pharmacokinetic parameters like T_{max} , $t_{1/2}$ and Kel using non-compartmental model by WinNonlin® (Version 2.1, Pharsight Corporation, Mountain View, CA, USA). The difference between concentrations of levodopa in brain by two groups was compared by 2000 bootstrap samples. The extent of difference between the formulations was determined by 5000 bootstrap samples^{7,8}.

Statistical analysis :

To estimate confidence interval, individual PK parameters for test and reference were calculated for each bootstrap sample. Test to reference ratio of each PK metrics was calculated against each bootstrap samples so that 5000 bootstraps produced 5000 individual PK metric ratio. Standard error of the ratio was calculated and finally 90% confidence interval was established using following formula, original ratio $\pm 1.645 \times$ standard error from bootstrap samples⁹. All the statistical analyses were performed using SAS V9.1.3 (SAS Institute Inc, USA).

The pharmacokinetic parameters of l-dopa following nasal administration in the presence and absence of c-dopa were compared using Student t-test. A *p*-value of less than 0.05 was considered significant and the differences between formulations were found to be insignificant. According to the Committee for Pharmaceutical and Medicinal Products (CPMP) bioequivalence guideline the 80% to 125% decision rule was applied to the 90% confidence interval for log transformed primary PK parameters¹⁰.

Results and discussion

A total of 120 animals had completed the study. The method demonstrated acceptable performance and was therefore suitable for the determination of l-dopa in animal brain in the present bioequivalence study. Under the described analytical conditions, the relationship between the concentration and peak area ratio was linear from 0.05 to 20 pg/mL as represented in Fig. 1 (LLOQ – 0.05 pg/mL, $Y = 0.000915X - 0.000429$, $R_2 = 0.9995$).

The C_{max} and AUC_t in brain for nasal administration in presence of c-dopa were found to be 98.46 pg/mL and 351.17 pg*hr/mL respectively. The C_{max} and AUC_t in brain for nasal administration in absence of c-dopa were found to be 92.34 pg/mL and 322.14 pg*hr/mL respectively. There was a rise in C_{max} and AUC_t in brain in presence of c-dopa but however there was no change in T_{max} (0.25 h).

The AUC_{inf} in brain after nasal administration of l-

dopa and c-dopa was 549. AUC_{inf} in brain when l-dopa was given alone was 604, this increased AUC_{inf} may be attributed to bioadhesive property of microspheres which increases residence time of drug in nose increasing transport across olfactory epithelium. Therefore, the absolute extent that reaches the circulation and the brain in the present nasal delivery system might be promising.

The ANOVA tests, followed by bootstrap, were used to assess the statistical significance of the differences between the results following test and reference administration. A *p*-value of less than 0.05 was considered significant. Data are presented as mean \pm S.E.M., unless stated otherwise.

p-value of two independent sample student t test (after 2000 bootstrap) AUC_t and C_{max} for nasal l-dopa and l-dopa+c-dopa administration in brain was found to be 0.025 and 0.042 respectively, which signifies there is a significant difference between two formulations with respect to C_{max} and AUC_t . In order to compare bioequivalence 90% CI after 5000 bootstrapping of geometric mean ratio (nasal l-dopa/nasal l-dopa + c-dopa) of PK metrics, C_{max} and AUC were estimated and found to be 96.94 (60.05–133.83) and 92.29 (66.54–118.04) respectively and its *p*-value was found to be 0.547 details of the same is presented in Table 1. This signifies there is no significant difference between two formulations. Hence it can be concluded that bioadhesive nasal microspheres containing l-dopa alone can be used for the treatment of Parkinson's disease.

Fig. 1. Standard calibration curve of levodopa concentration vs mean drug to internal standard (IS) peak area ratio ($n = 6$).

Table 1. Geometric mean ratio and 90% confidence interval for primary PK metrics of levodopa alone (E)/levodopa+carbidopa from nasal microspheres

PK metrics	Ratio	Standard deviation	Lower limit	Upper limit
C_{max}	96.94	± 0.2242	60.05	133.83
T_{max}	98.68	± 0.2359	59.86	137.49
AUC5	168.42	± 0.7955	37.55	299.28
AUC10	132.78	± 0.4193	63.79	201.76
AUC15	109.82	± 0.2388	70.53	149.10
AUC30	97.74	± 0.1620	71.08	124.39
AUC60	88.12	± 0.1210	68.21	108.02
AUC120	84.84	± 0.0940	69.36	100.31
AUC240	86.68	± 0.1044	69.49	103.87
AUC480	87.62	± 0.1477	63.33	111.92
AUC720	92.29	± 0.1565	66.54	118.04

PK - Pharmacokinetic, GMR - Geometric Mean Ratio.

Based on our results, the l-dopa nasal delivery system could be used as prn (as needed) dosing and as a good adjuvant therapy for Parkinson's disease patients who experience symptom fluctuation by l-dopa oral administration containing l-dopa.

Conclusion

Post formulation animal study result substantiate the importance of nasal microsphere containing l-dopa alone over nasal formulation containing l-dopa, c-dopa for the treatment of PD, as brain bioavailability of the l-dopa was substantially higher for microspheres. Hence it can

be concluded that bioadhesive nasal microspheres containing l-dopa can be successfully used in treatment of Parkinson's disease.

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